

Navigating the Rough Seas of 21-century Science

We live increasingly immersed in science, and increasingly confused by it. Every day, the media publish hundreds of news items, previews, and comments on the results of scientific research that appear to say everything and the opposite of everything, with the result of feeding anti-scientism instead of combating it. Some fundamental methodological and epistemological questions, which should constitute the obvious and taken-for-granted basis for any assessment of scientific claims or products, are being lost in a cognitive fog that now affects even many specialists in the field, let alone ordinary people. The following lines aim to offer a very small, but hopefully not negligible, contribution to finding our bearings again.

Were it not for the problem of complexity, and if every level of reality could be treated without loss through complete mathematical formalization, we could imagine a single fundamental science: physics.

Physics aims to describe and explain what exists: **everything** that exists. For a long time now, scientists have understood that, in order to provide an unambiguous and precise description of any existing phenomenon or entity, one must pass through mathematical relations. For this reason, every phenomenon, in order to be described correctly and completely, must pass through one or, much more often, several mathematical equations.

Almost simultaneously with the extraordinary success achieved in understanding and predicting natural phenomena, with immense consequences for the everyday life of all people, it became clear, however, that a purely and properly physical-mathematical description of natural phenomena was within reach of the human intellect and of human computational systems only for a very small subset of simple and/or simplified phenomena. These are the exceptions in the universe, although an extraordinarily fruitful exception, both in terms of substantial and conceptual understanding and in terms of practical consequences for each of our lives.

The norm in the universe, however, consists of complex systems and phenomena that cannot be described, within the limits of the human intellect, through the “no compromise” approach and formalism of physics.

God, if He exists, may contemplate absolute beauty and handle with ease the equation of everything and, above all, its solutions for every boundary condition; but this privilege is entirely denied to human beings. Hence the birth of chemistry, geology, biology, and so on. All these disciplines, at the cost of a massive renunciation of the complete and absolute validity of quantitative and mathematical formalism in the description of phenomena, have

nevertheless given us a quantitative and generalizable understanding, and a highly useful one from a practical point of view, of many complex phenomena and systems.

One of the prices to be paid in order to turn our structural and insurmountable cognitive limits into something positive is that **the** absolute scientific truth no longer exists: truths are instead categorized and typified in a hierarchical sense. If I say that two bodies attract each other with a force proportional to the product of their masses and inversely proportional to the square of their distance, or if I say that elevated levels of LDL cholesterol increase cardiovascular risk, in both cases I am saying things that are scientifically grounded; but their hierarchical level of truth is certainly not the same.

Since the earliest stages of the immense explosion of modern scientific progress, whose positive and revolutionary impact on people's lives has had no precedent in human history, especially from the nineteenth century onward, the scientific method, based on experimental evidence, whether confirmatory or falsifying, has been taken as a model to be applied to an ever-wider range of situations and disciplinary approaches.

We must not forget, however, that the experimental scientific method was born and developed, in its fundamental characteristics and procedures, to be applied to the physics of natural phenomena in the strict sense and, in its specific historical context, to mechanics, thermodynamics, and electromagnetism.

Today, the scientific method is nominally applied in virtually every disciplinary field: from medicine to pharmacology, from economics to psychology, from ecology to history. Alongside the universal and generalized spread of this kind of approach, increasingly evident and worrying limits are emerging regarding the informational robustness that derives from it.

What makes this process more dangerous and destabilizing is the fact that the scientific method has been conceived, developed, and so far perceived as absolutely and totally robust. Seminal experiments such as those of Michelson and Morley or Eötvös, or paradigmatic phenomena such as the photoelectric effect or the Compton effect, are immensely powerful symbols of highly robust evidence and truth.

The decisive point is that the strength of the scientific method does not automatically transfer, intact, to every object to which it is applied; and what was born as a method of maximum power in highly controllable contexts is now applied to domains that are increasingly complex, unstable, and difficult to isolate. The increasingly universal and horizontal application of the scientific method to every informational-cognitive branch of human experience has been accompanied by a weakening, imperceptible in each single frame but overall profoundly destabilizing, of the method's capacity for univocal objectification.

It is now part of our daily experience to be exposed to substantially contradictory or evidently superficial claims and information, all nevertheless labeled as "scientific." In pursuing the noble, but impossible, aim of giving absolute objectivity to all branches of knowledge, we risk losing it even in those few branches that truly possess it. And without those immense foundations on which all human progress of the last two centuries rests, we risk falling into an abyss whose bottom cannot be seen: we are far beyond mere creaking sounds.

We need to bring order among physics and mathematics; other sciences that are not fully exact, but are nevertheless quantifiable with satisfactory results when properly used and interpreted; and, finally, disciplines that study hypercomplex systems, often quantifiable only in partial, probabilistic, contextual ways that are strongly dependent on the conditions of observation, such as sociology, economics, much of medicine and psychology, along with many others.

We must recognize that, outside the circle of simple or fundamental physical phenomena, the scientific method possesses degrees of reliability, robustness, and generalizability that are not absolute. Failure to complete this process of perspectivization and relativization adequately would condemn us to an ever-greater increase in cognitive fog and, ultimately, to the rejection of rationality in the regulation of human and social life: exactly what is now dangerously happening, and whose harmful effects are echoing from many different directions around us in everyday life.